

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF RANDOMLY ORIENTED STRANDS THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

M. Selezneva¹, K. Kouwonou², L. Lessard^{1*}, P. Hubert¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, École de Technologie Supérieure, Montréal, Canada

* Corresponding author (Larry.Lessard@mcgill.ca)

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1 Introduction and motivation

There is an emerging interest in the aerospace industry in manufacturing components with intricate features, such as ribs, using discontinuous-fibre composite materials. The conventionally used continuous fibre (CF) composites are difficult to form, while the short fibre preforms used by the automotive industry lack the required mechanical properties. Material systems with long discontinuous fibres and high fibre volume fraction have the potential of filling the niche between the formability of short fibre preforms and performance of CF composites. A candidate material system is composed of randomly-oriented-strands (ROS) that can be used in compression moulding. This type of material is commercially available from material suppliers, such as Hexcel (HexMCTM with thermoset matrix) and TenCate (Cetex[®] MC1200 with thermoplastic-matrix). The feasibility of moulding complex components from ROS composites has been demonstrated by GreeneTweed [1]. However, a limited number of studies found in the open literature discuss processability and mechanical properties of these materials.

2 Literature review

Recent studies by Feraboli *et al.* [2-5], Van Wijngaarden *et al.* [6], Eugemann *et al.* [7] and Han *et al.* [8] investigated mechanical properties and formability of ROS materials. Feraboli *et al.* conducted an extensive investigation of mechanical properties of carbon-fibre thermoset-matrix ROS composites. They found that strength increased with longer strand lengths but was significantly lower than that of quasi-isotropic CF composites [2]. Modulus showed little dependence on length and was almost as high as that of CF composites [2]. It is also noteworthy that damage propagation appeared

to be uninfluenced by microstructural defects, such as voids and resin rich areas [2]. Authors attributed this behaviour to complex 2D interaction between strands [2]. Feraboli *et al.* also compared the response of unnotched and open-hole specimens under tensile and compressive loading [3]. They found that ROS material is essentially notch-insensitive, since not all specimens failed in the vicinity of an open-hole [3]. Authors also addressed the issue of variability in the modulus data by evaluating different measurement techniques which include an extensometer, strain gages of various lengths and the digital image correlation (DIC) technique [4]. Data obtained with the DIC technique depicted large strain variation on the surface of the specimen which makes extensometers and strain gages, even large ones, inadequate for global strain measurement [4]. Overall, the DIC technique was found to yield the most accurate and repeatable measurement of modulus by averaging the full-field strain values [4]. Finally, they developed a finite element method capable of capturing the variability of tensile modulus in the material [5].

Van Wijngaarden *et al.* demonstrated excellent formability of the carbon-fibre thermoplastic-resin preforms by moulding a deep flange [6]. Furthermore, carbon/PEEK ROS material was considered for manufacturing of door hinges for Eurocopter Germany [7]. This material is an attractive alternative for metals since it does not corrode, is lighter and cheaper to manufacture. It was found that both ROS and CF tapes met the design threshold. Overall, CF tapes are a more robust option in terms of material variability, whereas, ROS composites are more cost and time effective from the manufacturing standpoint since cutting and preforming is not required. Han *et al.* [8] explore the use of carbon/PEEK ROS for

manufacturing of bolted joints. For this application, they compared the use of fabric-only, ROS-only and hybrid composites. They found that bearing strength of ROS composites is 30% higher than that of fabric-only composites and that presence of fabric layers reduces the variability of properties [8]. Authors also presented a finite element technique for modeling bearing failure of ROS based composites [8]. These articles highlight some of the key properties of ROS composites, but the complete material characterization with respect to performance and processability is yet to be done.

3 Scope and objectives

A new multi-disciplinary study [9]-[10] is being conducted to systematically evaluate, characterize and model the moulding process and mechanical properties of composites manufactured from carbon/PEEK ROS, which can be seen in Fig. 1.

Objectives of this study are twofold. Firstly, the effect of strand length and panel thickness on mechanical properties is investigated. Secondly, the use of digital image correlation (DIC) for strain measurement, as an alternative to strain gages, is considered. The acquired knowledge about the influential parameters and the associate variability will aid with the future development of a stochastic model for prediction of mechanical properties.

4 Experimental methods

4.1 Manufacturing

The material is carbon/PEEK CYTEC APC-2/AS4 6.35 mm wide unidirectional slit tape with fibre volume fraction of 61%. An automated tape cutter (Kingsing Machinery Co. Limited, model KS-915) was used to cut this material into strands of desired lengths (12, 25 or 50 mm). A steel mould with cavity dimensions of 185 x 280 mm² was used for compression moulding. Strands were placed into the mould in small batches and shuffled each time to better control their distribution and to minimize their out-of-plane orientation. The mould was closed, placed into a pre-heated press (Wabash 100T) and pressure of 34 bars was applied. The mould temperature was increased up to 380°C and was maintained for 15 minutes. It was then cooled down to below 70°C at an approximate rate of 12°C/min and removed from the press.

4.2 Non-destructive testing

Prior to mechanical testing some of the panels were subjected to NDT inspections using thermography and through-transmission ultrasonic c-scan techniques. The resolution of the c-scan image is 1 mm and is meant to pick up large voids and delamination. Examples of these scans can be seen in Fig. 2. No major defects were detected by these inspections. The minor colour variation (i.e. signal strength) in these images can be attributed to small voids, thickness variations or non-uniformity of material properties, such as density and fibre orientation.

4.3 Mechanical testing

In order to evaluate the effect of strand length and panel thickness on tensile properties, six panels were fabricated with strand lengths of 12, 25 or 50 mm and panel thickness of 3 or 6 mm. For each set of parameters, six specimens were tested as per the ASTM D3039 standard. Specimens were 250 mm long and 25 mm wide, and had a gage section of 125 x 25 mm². Specimen width of 25 mm was used even though individual strands making up the material were as long as 50 mm. Earlier results [9] showed that specimen width (12 mm – 50 mm) had no effect on tensile strength and modulus of ROS panels with 25 mm long strands. A laser extensometer (MTS LX500) with a 75 mm gage length was used to measure strain. Specimens were loaded at a rate of 1 mm/min.

Results presented in Fig. 3a indicate that higher tensile strength is achieved with ROS panels that consist of longer strands. In the case of 3 mm thick panels, strength increases from 220 to 420 MPa as strand length increases from 12 to 50 mm. Nonetheless, even the highest strength obtained with 50 mm long strands is still significantly lower than that of quasi-isotropic CF laminates, which is approximately 850 MPa [11]. Performance of discontinuous fibre composites is known to be lower than that of CF composites in part due the reduced ability of short fibres to carry load. As the fibre length increases, mechanical properties are expected to increase eventually approaching the properties of CF composites. Theoretically, fibres can be treated as continuous when their length (L) is at least 50 times the critical length (L_c), which is defined by

$$L_c = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2\tau_i}$$

where σ_f is the fibre strength, d is the fibre diameter and τ_i is the interface shear strength [12]. For AS4/PEEK these values are approximately $\sigma_f = 3440$ MPa, $d = 7 \mu\text{m}$ and $\tau_i = 100$ MPa, hence $L_c = 0.115$ mm. Therefore, even the short 12 mm strands ($L/L_c = 100$) can be considered as continuous. Since the strength of ROS composites is low despite the fact that the continuity assumption is met, there must be other factors besides fibre length efficiency that influence strength. For one, the assumption of fibre continuity would ignore the adverse effect of fibre (or strand) ends which act as discontinuities or stress concentrations and can serve as sites for crack initiation. Also, the variability of the residual thermal stresses and strains would have to be taken into account.

It is also noteworthy, that high strength of the 3 mm panel with 50 mm long strands is also accompanied by high variability. This variability is related to the heterogeneous meso-structure of these specimens. ROS panels are expected to become more statistically homogeneous when they consist of smaller strands and have higher thickness.

From Fig. 3b, it appears that average modulus increases slightly with increasing strand length. However, statistical analysis using ANOVA in excel showed that due to large variability of the data, strand length does not affect modulus. Similarly, Feraboli *et al.* [2] showed that in the case of thermoset-matrix ROS composites strength increases with increasing strand length, while modulus is unaffected by it. The average modulus of all the panels is 40 GPa, which is approximately 70% of the modulus of quasi-isotropic CF laminates [11]. The fact that modulus is unaffected by strand length (in the range of 12-50 mm) is in line with the assumption of fibre continuity. Possible reasons for the reduction in modulus in comparison to CF laminates are fibre out-of-plane orientation (see section 4.5) and fibre curviness which result from strand compaction and flow during moulding.

Finally, one 6 mm thick panel with 25 mm long strands was used for compression testing. A total of

seven specimens were subjected to compressive loading as per the ASTM D3410 standard. Specimens were 150 mm long and 25 mm wide, and hence had a 25 x 25 mm² gage section. Specimens were loaded at 1.5 mm/min. It was found that tensile and compressive strengths are the same for this material, but that there is less scatter in compression data.

4.4 Application of DIC

The applicability of DIC was investigated by tracing the evolution of the strain-field on the surface of tensile specimens. Seven ROS specimens (25 mm long strands) and three unidirectional 90° CF specimens were used for this study. The black and white speckle pattern was created by spraying the already black specimens with white spray paint. Specimens were loaded at a rate of 1 mm/min and photos were taken with a 24 MP Nikon D3200 camera at a rate of 1 photo/second. Images were analyzed using VIC-2D (Correlated Solutions). For correlation, subset size of 65 pixels was used, which translates to a region of 2.5 x 2.5 mm².

For validation, a conventional contact extensometer with a gage length of 25 mm was used in conjunction with DIC during testing of CF specimens. The DIC technique was used to measure strain between the extensometer arms, as depicted in Fig. 4. The three white lines represent extensometer option in VIC-2D software and indicate strains between the endpoints (6940, 6960 and 7030 $\mu\epsilon$), whereas, the dash line shows strain measured by the contact extensometer (6610 $\mu\epsilon$). Overall, good correlation was observed, and modulus values measured with a conventional extensometer vs. the DIC extensometer were within 5% of each other.

The evolution of the strain-field on the surface of an ROS specimen is shown in Fig. 5. From this figure it is evident that the strain-field is non-uniform and that failure occurs in the vicinity of a hot-spot. Overall, up to three hot-spots were detected on the surface of a tensile specimen and they were noticeable even at low average strain values (500 $\mu\epsilon$). Since hot-spots have higher strain, and hence lower modulus, at any given load than the rest of the specimen, it can be postulated that material properties in that region are matrix-dominated in the longitudinal direction. Specimens failed by strand

pull-out, hence also indicating of matrix failure. Therefore, tensile strength of ROS specimens is dependent on the probability of having an area with properties that are largely matrix-dominated in the loading direction.

Stress-strain curves were constructed based on average surface strains calculated for each load (or photo). Comparison between the stress-strain curves of CF and ROS specimens is presented in Fig. 6. It should be noted that CF specimens are weaker and more compliant than ROS specimens, because they were tested in 90° or matrix direction. Large variability among the ROS specimens is evident, while the three curves of CF specimens coincide.

DIC permits for calculation of Poisson's ratio which was computed based on average surface strains, longitudinal and transverse. Fig. 7 summarizes strength, stiffness and Poisson's ratio of ROS tensile specimens. These values were normalized with respect to the average value of each parameter, which is given in the bottom of each bar graph. The error bars show the max and min values obtained. It is interesting to note, that variability of normalized tensile strength, modulus and Poisson's ratio is the same.

Variability of tensile properties can be quantified by computing the coefficient of variation. However, when it comes to DIC, data variability depends on the subset size (i.e. resolution). Variability and error are higher for small subsets, while average strains are not affected by the subset size. Hence, it was decided to use a subset size that would be representative of a strain gage size recommend by the ASTM D3039. Subset size of 171 pixels gives 6 mm x 6 mm gage section. Coefficients of variation of ROS and CF specimens are 29% and 4%, respectively.

Variability can be further visualized via histograms. Fig. 8 shows the evolution of strain-field histograms with increasing load for ROS (a) and CF (b) specimens. It is evident that histograms of ROS specimens are significantly more spread out.

4.5 Microscopy

After testing, the 3 mm thick specimens were cut for microscopy, see Fig. 9. Interestingly, no cracks were

observed in the micrographs. This observation suggests that failure occurs at a weak spot at a load, which is too low to cause damage throughout the entire specimen. The absence of cracks and delamination can be expected since specimens fail at load that is less than 50% of the expected failure stress of a quasi-isotropic CF laminate.

There was also a characteristic difference in the meso-structure in relation to the strand length. As can be seen in Fig. 9a, short strands have a high out-of-plane orientation. On the other hand, the long strands have a more planar and orderly orientation, as shown in Fig. 9b. This difference in orientation can be a contributing factor in the load bearing capabilities of ROS composites; longer more planar strands lead to a higher tensile strength.

4.6 Density

Density of the ROS panels was measured with the aim to analyse planar distribution of the fibre volume fraction. Micrographs did not show any voids in the material, so it was assumed that fibre volume fraction is directly related to density through the rule of mixtures. Density was measured as per the ASTM D792. A total of 40 samples with a surface area of 10 x 25 mm² were cut from panels with 12 and 50 mm long strands. This sample size was used in order to have the smallest possible samples that weight at least 1g, as recommended by the standard. Overall, density measurements showed little scatter and the coefficient of variation was 2%. Hence, it can be said that fibre volume fraction is uniform on that scale. On the contrary, if DIC data points are averaged over an area equivalent to 250 mm², coefficient of variation for ROS specimens is still high at 22%.

5 Conclusions

Work presented in this paper shows that mechanical properties of the ROS material are highly variable on the meso-scale. Variability within a specimen can be quantified with DIC analysis which showed that coefficient of variation of strain on the surface of a tensile specimen is 29% (Fig. 5). Similarly, strength, modulus and Poisson's ratio can vary by 30% with respect to the average values of all the specimens (Fig. 7). It can be postulated that other properties, such as coefficient of thermal expansion, are also variable on the meso-scale. Hence, it is important to

consider this variability when trying to characterize and model ROS composites or design with them. For measuring strain or deformation it is preferred to use the DIC technique since it can capture the entire strain-field on the surface of the specimen. The next step in this project encompasses modeling of mechanical properties, and the probabilistic approach seems to be the most suitable for this task.

It was found that strand length affects tensile strength. The lower strength obtained with 12 mm long strands can be related to the higher number of strand ends and/or higher out-of-plane orientation which are inherent to shorter strands or fibres. The effect of strand size will be investigated further. Another important parameter to consider is fibre or strand curviness, particularly in the case of high strand flow. Hence, specimens obtained from flat panels are not necessarily representative of complex parts that require high material flow during moulding. That issue will have to be considered in future works.

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Unidirectional tape

Chopped strands

Compression moulding

ROS panel

Fig. 1. Manufacturing cycle.

Fig. 2. Examples of a) ROS panel, b) thermography scan and c) through-the-thickness ultrasonic c-scan.

Fig. 3. The effect of strand length and panel thickness on a) strength and b) modulus. The error bars show the max and min normalized values.

Fig. 4. Comparison between extensometer and DIC strain measurement for a CF specimen. The three white lines represent extensometers in VIC-2D software and indicate strain between the endpoints. The dashed line shows strain (6610 $\mu\epsilon$) measured by the contact extensometer.

Fig. 5. Evolution of the strain-field on the surface of a 3 mm thick ROS specimen subjected to tensile loading as captured by DIC. Strands are 6.35 mm wide and 25 mm long.

Fig. 6. Comparison between the stress-strain curves of 3 mm thick CF (red) and ROS (blue) specimens. Strands are 6.35 mm wide and 25 mm long.

Fig. 7. Summary of strength, modulus and Poisson's ratio of 3 mm thick ROS specimens tested with DIC. Strands are 6.35 mm wide and 25 mm long. Values are normalized based on the average, which is shown in the bottom. The error bars show the max and min normalized values.

Fig. 8. Evolution of the strain histograms with increasing loading, which correspond to a) ROS and b) CF specimens.

Fig. 9. Micrographs of 3 mm thick ROS samples with a) 12 mm and b) 50 mm long strands. Both images were taken from the gage section of failed tensile specimens.

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